

TEACHING ENGLISH THROUGH ICTI

Kurbanbaeva Mirigul Jenisbaevna

Student at the Faculty of Foreign Languages, English Language and Literature, Nukus State Pedagogical Institute named after Ajiniyaz

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12742243>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 5-iyul 2024 yil
Ma'qullandi: 8-iyul 2024 yil
Nashr qilindi: 15-iyul 2024 yil

KEY WORDS

information and communication technologies, increasing motivation, person-oriented approach, communicative competence.

ABSTRACT

The article discusses the possibilities of using information and communication technologies in the process of teaching English, identifies the goals of using ICT in English lessons, and characterizes the types of activities that contribute to the effective learning of the material.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, there is an active process of informatization in the field of education, which involves the introduction and use of new information technologies, the use of communication means that can be useful in the formation of an intellectually developed personality who is well versed in the information space.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In modern science, there are many different definitions of the term "information and communication technologies". According to the Pedagogical Dictionary (edited by Dr. L.M. Luzina), information and communication technologies (ICT) are a set of means and methods for converting information data to obtain information of a new quality (information product).

The main goals of using ICT in English lessons are [1]:

1. increasing motivation to learn the language, interest in the subject, desire to communicate in a foreign language;
2. development of speech competence: the ability to understand authentic foreign language texts, as well as the ability to convey information grammatically and lexically correctly;
3. expanding the volume of knowledge about the culture of the country of the language being studied;
4. development of ability and readiness for independent learning of the English language.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In modern education, electronic media are increasingly used as sources of information. Each foreign language lesson should be aimed at practical results, at achieving communicative competence, i.e. a certain level of linguistic, regional knowledge, communication skills and speech skills that allow foreign language communication. The use of ICT in lessons allows you to diversify the learning process, present educational material more visually, accessible and interesting for each student. The use of ICT in the study of foreign languages contributes to: the development of students' creative capabilities and abilities; creating conditions for students'

self-education in areas of knowledge that interest them; increasing the level of use of visuals in the classroom; increasing lesson productivity; establishing interdisciplinary connections; acquiring real experience of intercultural communication in a foreign language; enriching students' knowledge about the history and culture of the countries of the language being studied; developing the ability to navigate the modern foreign language information environment. Thus, the use of ICT helps to speed up the learning process, increase students' interest in the subject, improves the quality of learning the material, allows for individualization of the learning process and makes it possible to avoid subjectivity in assessment. Foreign language lessons using ICT are distinguished by their variety, increased interest of students in a foreign language, and efficiency. When organizing a lesson using computer programs, information is provided to students colorfully, using animation effects, in the form of text, diagrams, graphs, drawings. All this makes it possible to explain the educational material more clearly and accessibly than orally. It is very important that in such lessons the student can work individually, moving forward in learning new material at his own pace, returning to something unclear if required, or studying further.

But, nevertheless, every teacher must remember that a computer in the educational process is not a teacher, a substitute or an analogue of the teacher himself, a computer is a means of children's development that enhances and expands the capabilities of his cognitive activity. The computer provides the teacher with the opportunity to free up time for creative activities and create individual educational routes for students. The resource capabilities of the Internet educational environment allow the use of new interactive materials and manuals, and also enable the teacher to independently develop presentations with materials.

To organize a student-oriented educational process, foreign language teachers need to master the methodology of using ICT tools.

The most commonly used ICT tools in the educational process include [2]:

- computer and multimedia projector,
- educational resources on the Internet,
- electronic textbooks and manuals,
- simulators and testing programs,
- DVDs and CDs with pictures and illustrations, video and audio materials,
- research works and projects.

The possibility of using ICT tools in teaching a foreign language is extremely wide. As an English teacher, I see a number of advantages of using ICT both in class and in extracurricular activities. In my lessons, I often use presentations, both when explaining new material and when practicing and consolidating. It is worth noting that you should not overload your presentation with text. The selection of material for presentation must comply with the principles of science, accessibility, and clarity. Updating knowledge often takes place in the form of a conversation with students. The questions of such a conversation should be shown on slides, but not in the form of simple text (this is especially true for teaching primary school students). Questions can be presented with a short video, photo, or drawing. When recalling the material you have studied, you can cite several slides from a previous presentation, and their design does not need to be changed to match the new background; associative memory works better this way.

CONCLUSION

In the process of work, I came to the conclusion that computer technology helps:

- make classes more visual;
- provide the educational process with new, previously unavailable materials that help students demonstrate their creative abilities;
- to accustom students to work independently with the material; attract passive listeners;
- provide instant feedback;
- to intensify the cognitive activity of students, and, consequently, the desire to study the subject;

- objectively evaluate the actions of students.

REFERENCES:

1. Galskova N.D. Modern methods of teaching foreign languages. M., 2020.
2. Biboletova M.Z. Multimedia tools as an assistant to the teaching and learning complex "Enjoy English" for secondary school // Foreign languages at school, 2019. No. 3.
3. Naryshkina E.A. Using computer programs in teaching English // Internet magazine Festival of Pedagogical Ideas "Open Lesson", 2017, 2018.

